

THE ROLE OF BUKHARA IN THE LIFE OF THE SAMANID STATE (HISTORICAL AND SOURCE ANALYSIS)

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Abstract: This article analyzes the role of Bukhara in the life of the Samanid state on the basis of historical and source data.

Keywords: Bukhara, the Great Silk Road, civilization, Samanids, Ismail Samani, Islam, Farjak madrasah, Samanid mausoleum.

Long considered a link between East and West, an important center on the Great Silk Road, Bukhara occupied an unsurpassed place in the history of world civilization. "In the X-XII centuries Bukhara became a great place of science and culture not only in the East, but throughout the world" [1].

Throughout the history of the Sasanian state and statehood, many construction and creative works were carried out in Bukhara, science flourished. In particular, during the reign of Ismail Samani (892-907), stability and peace were established in Bukhara, the strengthening of which began to attract attention. Ismail dealt a crushing blow to the steppe people, attacking the Sasanian nomads and subjugating the city of Taraz in 893. It was one of the biggest campaigns against the nomads in the time of the Samanids. This has led to the fact that the settlers' raids on Mawarannahr have ended, and the local population has now completely got rid of incredibly heavy grief and anxiety about the construction of defensive walls and a huge number of forts in the country and their constant repair. It is from this period that the annual construction of the Kampirak wall surrounding Bukhara begins. For Ismail Samani believed in his powerful troops and said: "As long as I live, I will be the wall of the Bukhara region."

The prosperity of Transoxiana offended the Arab Caliphate from day to day, which was deprived of huge wealth, on the one hand, and raged on the other.

Therefore, the struggle between the Saffarids and the Samanids, which eventually began between them in 900, ends with the victory of Ismail Samani. Thus, thanks to the heroism of Ismail Samani, Transoxiana will be completely freed from the influence of the Arab Caliphate at the end of the ninth century. Ismail Samani united Transoxiana as a powerful state, making Bukhara his capital.

The role and influence of Islam in the development of the Sasanian state was extremely high, and even in the eastern world Bukhara became known as one of the most famous centers of Islam. Many temples were built in the cities, including the Jameh Mosque, Khomeini Mosque and houses of worship. During this period, the first madrasah in Central Asia was built in Bukhara. This ancient madrasah of Bukhara was built in the X century. It was called Farjak madrasah.

Farjak Madrasah is one of the oldest madrasahs in Bukhara, burned down in May-June 937 AD. Abu Bakr Muhammad an-Narshahi gave the following information about this madrasah: "Again, during the reign of Amir Said Nasr ibn Ahmad ibn Ismail, in the month of Rajab of the year 325 (May-June 937), a fire fell on Bukhara and burned down all markets. Grass started with a halimpaz shop. The store is located at the gates of Samarkand, and the khalimpaz brought the ashes from the bottom of the Halim pot to the roof and wanted to fill it up, since there was a hole in the roof. Among the ashes there is a piece of coal. Halimpaz did not notice this, and the wind carried the smoldering coals and hit the house of reeds. He set fire to the house, and from him the fire spread to the entire market. Fire floated across the sky like a cloud. "Koyi Bikor" (Maiden Street), bazaar shops, Farjak madrasah, market-changers and bazoso, Farjak bazaar, money-changers and bazoso, everything on this side of Bukhara up to the anhor lip was burned" [2].

Later, the madrasah was renovated. The 12th-century author Abdukarim al-Samani wrote that the madrasah was located in front of the Farjak gate. Farjak and Samarkand were two names for the same gate. Ibn al-Awfi, who lived in the 13th century, wrote in his book *Jawomi al-Hikaya* that he studied at the Farjak Madrasah with the teacher Mas'ud Imamza. The madrasah also operated during the Mongol

period. Farjak is one of the oldest and first madrasahs in Bukhara. According to some researchers, this madrasah was the first madrasah in the Muslim world [3].

The spiritual life of the country was led by the leaders of religion and science, called "masters". Later this name was glorified by the name "Sheikh ul-Islam". After the teacher there were khatibs. At their own expense, the Somanites allocated special places for the construction of mosques, madrasahs and houses, as well as large estates. The development of Islam undoubtedly played an important role in the formation of the peoples of Central Asia as an independent people.

Also during the reign of Ismail Somani, he performed many architectural and construction works. The Mausoleum of Somani was built in the 9th century by order of the founder of the dynasty, Ismail Somani. The building is located in the center of the garden on the site of an ancient tomb and is the dakhma of the famous dynasty (875-999). Inside it are three graves, one of which belongs to Ahmad ibn Ismail, the son of Ismail Samani. However, there is no clear information that Ismail himself was buried here. When Genghis Khan was approaching the city, the people of Bukhara completely buried the mausoleum of the somonites. They knew that Genghis Khan's army would destroy everything in its path. Therefore, instead of a beautiful structure, the army saw a small hill and passed by it. After the danger had passed, the people of Bukhara carefully dug up the mausoleum. The Somanite tomb was discovered and restored in the 20th century. Previously, it was completely hidden by centuries-old cultural layers. As in the Middle Ages, the mausoleum of the Samanids is considered a masterpiece of Central Asian architecture and a real pearl of world architecture [4].

In a word, ancient and eternal Bukhara is a city with a rich and unique history of its formation, which is measured in millennia, and is known to the whole world for its contribution to the development of cultural, educational, spiritual and religious value. I left So, the initiative and leadership of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, modern projects and solutions make our Sharif city even more beautiful and turn it into a real pearl of the East. Bukhara, with its ancient and modern

appearance, will continue to enchant the people of the world with its history and artifacts for many centuries.

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